

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

China–Latin America Relations in the Modern Day; Economic Perspective

Marion Makaria Massaquoi

College of Liberal Arts, Shanghai University, China.

Accepted

January 31, 2022

Published

February 17, 2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.
Marion Makaria Massaquoi

Self-Payment

*Corresponding Author:

Funding:

How to cite this article (APA) Marion Makaria Massaquoi (2022). China–Latin America Relations in the Modern Day; Economic Perspective. North American Academic Research, 5(1), 137-161. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6110930>

ABSTRACT

Notwithstanding the emergence of a rich literature on the upsurge of China in Latin America (LAC) since 2000, we are still grappling with this marvel. In this article we seek to theorize this expanding South–South relationship from two vantage points. First, from the perspective of China, we argue that, by necessity, the PRC has had to internationalize its development strategy in order to compensate for its serious natural resource deficit, feed the world’s largest domestic population, and fuel the soon-to-be largest economy in the world. LAC has been just one slice of China’s ‘go out’ strategy. Our second perspective probes the effect of China’s entry into the region. Through the lens of development economics, we identify three separate political economy scenarios that have been accentuated within those countries that have the strongest economic ties with China. We rely on measures of institutional performance and macro-economic trends to illustrate the variable effects of China on LAC.

Keywords

China; Latin America; resource recession; free trade agreements; FDI; neo-dependency theory, PRC

Introduction

It would be difficult to exaggerate the sea change that has occurred within the Latin American and Caribbean region (LAC) as a result of the phenomenal rise of the People’s Republic of China (PRC) within the international political economy over the past three decades. With its entry into the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, China crossed a new threshold in its ambitious export-led development model. The country’s heightened demand for copper, crude oil, iron ore, soybeans and fishmeal kicked off a decade-long commodity lottery from 2003 to 2013 which saw the unit price on these raw materials increase 2–3 times over this decade. LAC countries with an abundance of these natural resources, like Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Peru, sold directly to China and made out handsomely. Countries like Mexico, which sells most of its commodity exports to the USA and other markets, benefitted indirectly from the China-driven commodity price boom. After

averaging 9–10% annual growth rates for some 30 years, China's gross domestic product (GDP) has slowed to an average annual growth rate of 6–7% since 2013.

According to Beijing, this is partly an intentional shift away from industrial exports and toward services, technology, and domestic consumption. The pass-through for LAC in terms of China's lower demand for commodities has been a slowing of growth to 1–2% on average since 2013, versus an annual average growth rate of 4.8% between 2003 and 2013. However, unlike past commodity booms, where trade bonds waned once demand had slowed and prices plummeted, China's economic ties and presence in the LAC region continue to hold strong. It is this commitment to stick around that has triggered debates concerning China's 'true' intentions in the region, whether this represents a challenge to US hegemony in the Western Hemisphere, and whether the trade and investment asymmetries that have come to characterize China–LAC economic relations are simply a replication of earlier patterns of dependent development in the Latin American region. This current juncture is the impetus for this article. Total China–LAC trade increased 20-fold between 2000 and 2016 and as of 2016 China accounted for 9% of LAC's exports and 16% of its imports (UN Comtrade ITS). Over this same time period, China's outflows of foreign direct investment (OFDI) in LAC totaled \$113.6 billion, with roughly half constituting new OFDI and the remainder accounting for mergers and acquisitions (Dussel Peters & Velasquez, 2017, p. 4).¹ In 2015 alone, lending to Latin America from China's two big policy banks – China Development Bank (CDB) and China Export-Import Bank (CHEXIM) – was higher than combined funds lent to the LAC region that same year by western multilateral banks (Ray, Gallagher, & Sarmiento, 2016, p.1). According to statements made by Chinese President Xi Jinping at a forum hosted by Beijing in January 2015 with 33 member countries of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States, the Chinese government is committed to doubling China–LAC trade to US\$500 billion by 2025 and to investing US\$250 billion in Latin America over the next decade (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean [ECLAC], 2015). Initially, some referred to China's burgeoning economic ties with LAC as 'soft power' (Ellis, 2009).

However, we would argue that this term is much too banal to account for these hefty numbers. Despite the emergence of a rich literature on the political economy of China–LAC relations (Gallagher, 2016; Gallagher & Porzecanski, 2011; Hearn & Leon Manriquez, 2011; Myers & Wise, 2016), we are still scratching the surface in terms of our grasp of this phenomenon. Thus far, data analyses and deep description have been the dominant approaches, which makes sense given that the rise of China in the Latin American region is fairly recent. Unfortunately, the debates swirling around this subject – China as a threat to US hegemony and the neo-dependent nature of the China–LAC relationship – have been downright unimaginative. In this article, we take a first step toward theorizing this rapidly growing South–South relationship from two vantage points. First, from the perspective of China, we argue that, by necessity, the PRC has had to internationalize its

development strategy in order to compensate for its serious natural resource deficit, feed the world's largest domestic population, and fuel the soon-to-be largest economy in the world. This internationalized development model has been made possible by China's accumulation of the world's highest level of foreign exchange reserves, which sat at US \$3.06 trillion in July 2017.

Our second perspective probes the effect of China's entry into the LAC region since the turn of the millennium. Now that the dust has settled on the post-boom period, the effect of LAC's tighter economic integration with China has come more clearly into focus. Taking the literature on development economics as our guidepost, we identify three separate political economy scenarios that have been accentuated within those countries that have the strongest trade links and OFDI inflows from China: the first scenario is the decision of Chile, Costa Rica, and Peru to institutionalize their respective relationships with China through the negotiation of separate bilateral free trade agreements (FTAs) with the PRC; the second scenario is the institutional resource curse that struck Argentina and Brazil in the throes of the China boom; and, the third scenario is Mexico's competitive disadvantage vis-versal China as it persists with a neoliberal export-led industrial strategy but a minimal public policy framework to guide it.

The article proceeds in three parts. The following section sets a baseline for China– LAC a relation which traces the nature of cross-Pacific political and economic exchange prior to the 2003–2013 booms. A third section subjects the current debates to closer scrutiny, explains why they are wanting, and expands on our interpretation of China's growing presence in the LAC region as reflective of the country's need to internationalize its development strategy. A fourth section turns to our country groupings, where we draw on the discipline of development economics to situate the patterns that have emerged as a result of China's closer economic integration with the LAC region. A final section summarizes our findings and offers conclusions about the China–LAC relationship moving forward.

Materials and methods

Add your text here. Times new roman 12 points. 1.5 space.

A brief historical backdrop to China LAC relations

Long before the normalization of diplomatic ties between China and the six LAC countries considered here, and even amidst the US embargo against trade with China, 'people- to-people' commercial relations had been established between China and various LAC countries.² For example, Argentina and Mexico both sold wheat to the PRC in the early 1960s as a severe drought and the mismanagement of grain stocks under Chairman Mao Zedong's Great Leap Forward led to widespread death and famine (Dikotter,2010). Large Chinese-sponsored trade exhibitions were staged in both Chile and Mexico in 1964, resulting in numerous informal bilateral deals to promote trade between private actors in China and in these host countries (Connelly &

Bustamante, 1992, pp. 133–135). By the 1970s, Brazil was trading iron ore in exchange for Chinese oil; China had become the third largest buyer of Chilean copper and Chile was importing back from China light industrial goods, chemical products, tools, and machinery (Joseph, 1985, p. 140). Mexican producers, moreover, had met with considerable success in selling value-added manufactured goods to their Chinese counterparts.

Despite these growing economic ties, from roughly 1949 to 1979 cross-Pacific relations were weighted more heavily toward politics. First, were the efforts of the PRC to gain diplomatic recognition from afar and to isolate the ‘renegade province’ of Taiwan (Republic of China, or ROC); second, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) also saw Latin America as a recruiting ground for fellow radicals of a socialist-communist bent (Deckers, 1989). Cuba’s revolutionary victory of 1959 and the eventual siding of Fidel Castro with the Soviets against the PRC saw the majority of LAC leftist political parties and would-be revolutionaries follow suit. Yet, China continued to pursue its people-to-people strategy in Latin America, still looking to spruce up its foreign image and to drum up business deals. It was Mexican President Luis Echeverria’s impassioned speech before the United

Nations in 1971, which argued for the expulsion of Taiwan and the admission of China in its place, which rallied the vote for China’s entry into the UN later that same year (Mora, 1997). By 1974, Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Mexico, and Peru had all formally recognized the PRC and normalized diplomatic relations with Beijing – five years earlier than the opening of the US embassy there. China’s 1966–1976 Cultural Revolution put a damper on China–LAC ties, although political and economic exchanges were resurrected by the mid-1970s. Up until the late 1970s China continued to voice political support for LAC on issues of sovereignty, economic justice, and the right to self-determination. Following the 1989 military massacre of Chinese student protesters in Tiananmen Square, China was widely condemned by the West. Perhaps the one exception was the LAC countries which, for better or worse, actively reached out in hosting delegations of distinguished Chinese officials in the immediate aftermath of this tragedy. Post-Tiananmen, however, the CCP had dropped its rhetorical political support for fellow revolutionaries and developing countries and stuck mainly to economic exchanges and business relations. By 1990, five LAC countries dominated trade with China in the following order: Brazil, Chile, Argentina, Peru, and Mexico. Total trade (exports and imports) between these countries and China was around US\$1.8 billion in 1988. By 2000 that same figure had jumped to about US\$10.5 billion. For the first four South American countries, the same products (iron ore, copper, and soybeans) have topped the list of exports to China since the forging of these trade ties. By 2000, Mexico registered the highest total trade with China, but of note here is that its trade with China had burgeoned on the import side. Since 1989 Mexico has consistently traded at a deficit with China; in 2016 this deficit hit US\$64.1 billion and accounts for some 85% of the LAC trade deficit with China (UN Comtrade ITS, 2017).

Up through the 1980s the LAC countries carried a trade surplus with China for most years; during the people-to-people trade years from 1949 to 1979, producers in the LAC region actually complained that their Chinese counterparts were not turning out the quality or kinds of goods they sought to buy. Of course, the tables have now turned, although Mexico has since been the only country to consistently carry a trade deficit with China. Apart from Mexico and Costa Rica, from which China purchases a small amount of value-added manufactured goods, the remainder of the countries considered here (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Peru) have exponentially increased their sales of commodities to China, but with little diversification of their exports to China.

The Hot debates

As our historical overview suggests, Washington had little cause for alarm over the China–LAC relationship during the twentieth century. Academics were similarly complacent and even optimistic about growing China–LAC ties during this same time frame (Li, 1991). However, the PRC’s meteoric rise in the Western Hemisphere since the early 2000s has invoked concern from both quarters. In 2005, one former Republican Congressman went so far as to interpret ‘China’s actions in Latin America as the movement of a hegemonic power into the hemisphere’ (Burton, 2005). In the academic realm, realist gurus like John Mearsheimer and Stephen Walt have recently argued that Washington must focus on ‘preserving U.S. dominance in the Western Hemisphere’ (Mearsheimer & Walt, 2016, p. 71). On the more dovish academic side, a new cottage industry of neo-dependency writers has sprung to life, most cautioning about the steep investment asymmetries and the old-fashioned pattern of comparative advantage that have become the defining features of China’s OFDI and trade relationship with South America, in particular (Laufer, 2013; Puyana & Costantino, 2015). In this section, we critique and respond to these debates.

China’s incursion on US sovereignty

With the founding of the PRC in 1949, and following the atrocities of Japanese occupation up through World War II, China has repeatedly declared its stance as one of non-intervention and peaceful coexistence. While some within its own Asian sphere of influence may beg to differ, in the Western Hemisphere there is simply no evidence that China’s tighter economic integration with Latin America amounts to more than just that. Especially since its entry into the WTO, China has actively engaged in every region of the global economy and with developed and developing countries alike (Bräutigam, 2009). It has become the top emerging market destination for FDI and has risen to the upper ranks of world trade more quickly than any other developing country since World War II. In just a decade, China has displaced Germany as the top exporter of

goods to the rest of the world and in this process become ‘the number-one high technology manufacturer in the world’ (Gallagher & Porzeczanski, 2011, p. 8). In essence, China’s participation in Latin America is just one slice of a much larger pie.

Nevertheless, China’s detractors insist that this scenario ‘challenges the America-led liberal world order,’ even if hard evidence of this alleged encroachment into the Western Hemisphere is scarce (Pei, 2010). For example, a quick comparison of Chinese and U.S. arms sales shows that in 2015 the USA accounted for 41% of arms transfer agreements with developing nations and China just 9% (Theohary, 2016). From 2012 to 2015, the USA and Western Europe averaged 66% of arms sales to LAC, whereas China averaged 16.3%. In contrast, around 46% of China’s arms sales went to Africa (36.4%) and Asia (10%) between 2012 and 2015. Based on these figures, even the hawkish US-China Economic and Security Commission has conceded that China poses no serious threat to the USA at this time (Piccone, 2016, p. 24).

Similar to the arms dominance of the USA and its western allies in Latin America, US trade and investment flows to LAC still tower over those between China and the LAC region. On trade, in 2016 total trade (exports and imports) between China and Latin America amounted to nearly US\$213 billion (UN Comtrade ITS), whereas total US–LAC trade was about US\$758 billion that same year. On FDI, the USA accounted for 20% of LAC’s OFDI inflows in 2014 (US\$31.8 billion), compared with China’s 6% share that same year (US\$9.5 billion) (Council on Foreign Relations, 2015). It is true that China is now the top destination for exports from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Peru and it has become the second most important partner in terms of total trade for Argentina, Chile, Colombia, and Peru (ECLAC, 2015, p. 28). Yet, in the bigger scheme of things Latin America is still a rather minor player in China’s ‘go out’ strategy and internationalized development model.

With the decision of the Trump administration to rip up the 12-member Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) agreement the USA dealt a blow to LAC TPP members, Chile, Mexico, and Peru, prompting them to pivot more toward China (Xinhua News, 2017). In August 2017, team Trump launched talks for the renegotiation of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) around its ‘America first’ pledge, which could further strengthen China’s economic ties in LAC. The North American auto sector is especially at risk, as NAFTA has fostered sophisticated patterns of cross-border production based on its 62.5% rule of origin (or content rule) in this sector. US (re)negotiators are now insisting that these auto sector content rules be raised to 85% and that 50% of content originate in the USA. Although this is the one sector where China has yet to gain a strong foothold, these self-defeating US demands could well augur the end of NAFTA. According to one former US trade official, ‘This is a huge gift to our competitors, if we move in this direction of making the

U.S. and the North American economy less competitive they must be pinching themselves in Beijing with where the administration is taking our trade policies' (Behsudi, 2017).

The dependency school revival

If anything, the rise of China in the global economy should be the final nail in the dependency school's coffin. With their emphasis on the structure of international capitalism as the independent variable, dependency scholars, 'neo' or otherwise, are still at a loss to explain the economic transformation of China: per capita GDP was US\$182 at the outset of the reform era in 1979, but soared to US\$7,924 by 2015. China's total GDP was about US\$76.9 billion in 1979, but now stands at around US\$10.9 trillion. In an earlier era, it was the authentic leaps forward of Japan, Taiwan, and South Korea, from 'poor' (10% or less of US per capita GDP) to 'rich' (50% of US per capita GDP) countries (Kroeber, 2016, pp. 9–10), which prompted a rich body of research on the Asian developmental state (Gereffi & Wyman, 1990). This later work confirmed the superior explanatory power of domestic interests and institutions, meaning that the dependency school has always been adept at describing policy failures and downward mobility in the developing world, but at a continual loss to explain these successful Asian breakout cases (Frieden 1991, p. 235).

With regard to the political economic dynamics that have been unfolding since the explosion of China–LAC trade and investment ties in the 2000s, the two most common neo-dependency school diagnoses have been 'unequal exchange' and the 'resource curse.' Unequal exchange refers to the dependence of a developing region like LAC on primary exports, which are plagued by cyclical price downturns, and the reliance of these countries on the import of manufactured goods, for which prices tend to rise in an upward secular pattern. This concept became a mainstay of the dependency school's emphasis on this core-periphery relationship, which was cast as the perpetuator of underdevelopment. The 'Resource Curse' relates to a country's dependence on commodity exports at the expense of the industrial sector, job creation, and sound macroeconomic policy-making (Pastor & Wise, 2015; Ross, 2015).

On the question of unequal exchange, with the exception of Costa Rica and Mexico, it is true that the pattern of commercial exchange between China and its South American partners has mirrored the old fashioned comparative advantage model that existed in the region at the turn of the last century. Another reality is the asymmetrical nature of the China–LAC relationship in terms of FDI. Total LAC OFDI in China from 2002 to 2012 is estimated to be around US\$917 million (Inter-American Development Bank, 2014), while Chinese OFDI in LAC was about US\$9.2 billion in 2012 alone (ECLAC, 2015, p. 34). Yet, whereas the earlier experience with this pattern of trade and FDI inspired policies of import-substitution industrialization (ISI)

and a widespread critique concerning the unfavourable terms of trade for the region (Prebisch, 1950), the structural conditions that now prevail within most of these economies are radically different.

With the exception of Chile and Peru, considerable inroads have been made with industrialization in the LAC region and this takes much of the wind out of these independency claims. For example, in the period from 2000 to 2016, manufactured goods accounted for about 45% of exports on average from Brazil, 61.8% from Costa Rica, and 78.4% from Mexico (UN Comtrade TPD). Moreover, for all but Costa Rica and Mexico, the terms of trade during the China boom were highly favourable for LAC. The downside of this story is that, although forward linkages in terms of manufactured exports have clearly improved in LAC, backward linkages to the domestic market are still too weak. This is the case with Mexico, for example, where manufacturing production is tied to

OFDI to the extent that local producers of intermediate goods are still not competitive as suppliers in these production zones.³ put simply, LAC emerging economies (EEs) have not kept pace with the competitiveness gains that China has registered in its manufacturing sector over the past 20 years, advances based on highly focused policies in the realm of science and technology. If there is a resource curse at work here, it is of an institutional nature and has to do with reform backsliding and institutional neglect (Mehlum, Moene, & Torvik, 2006).

China's internationalized development model: LAC as a partner and recipient in the 'go out' strategy

For the PRC, the story of the rise of China in Latin America is yet another angle on the phenomenal economic progress of this country since policy-makers there declared their 'reform and opening' project in 1979, followed by their 'go out' strategy in 1999. However, despite projecting the image of a behemoth Asian developmental state, China faces serious natural resource constraints and by necessity has had to incorporate select resource-rich EEs in Africa, South-East Asia, and increasingly Latin America into its internationalized development strategy. Through numerous joint ventures China is basically contributing to the development of select LAC countries so as to render them stronger partners in the provision of primary exports and the kinds of market opportunities which China seeks to propel its own growth and development.

China's unique status as a capital-abundant EE reflects its tenacious pursuit of an export-led development model – much like the earlier Japanese and South Korean strategies – based on a large pool of cheap labour, low domestic consumption, an undervalued currency, and in the case of China, enormous economies of scale. However, as in Japan and South Korea, this approach has run its course in China. Cheap labour and undervalued exchange rates are now a thing of the past. With the mixed returns and saturation of domestic investment in big infrastructure and industrial projects, Chinese policy-makers and entrepreneurs are now

hard-pressed to put these funds to more productive and efficient use. At a time when the western multilateral banks are focused on poverty reduction and the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (Gallagher, 2016, p. 72), China has stepped in to fund projects that fill crucial infrastructure gaps in emerging regions as part of its own internationalized development strategy.

In our introduction we ticked off the global figures on China–LAC trade (see Figure 1) and Chinese OFDI in LAC (see Table 1). China’s outgoing OFDI into massive resource related infrastructure projects within the EEs has been going on for about a decade. A combination of OFDI and policy bank lending, the latter totalling about US\$125 billion from CDB and CHEXIM as of 2016 (Gallagher & Myers, 2016), has gone to various LAC countries for building ports, roads, railways, dams, and nuclear power plants (Ellis, 2014). Already, there is beginning to be a shift in the sectorial makeup of Chinese OFDI away from straight resource exploitation and toward related manufacturing and services activities – which averaged more than half of Chinese OFDI to LAC from 2001 to 2016 (Dussel Peters & Velasquez, 2017, p. 4). Embedded in China’s 13th Five-Year Plan is a manifesto issued by the Central Committee of the CCP which indicates that competition and efficiency will underpin the overhaul of Chinese fiscal, financial, foreign trade, and OFDI policies (Myers, 2016).

Figure 1: Total trade between China and the LAC-6 countries, 1993–2016. Source: UN Comtrade ITS. Retrieved from <http://comtrade.un.org/>

With regard to Latin America, China’s reforms could have significant multiplier and spill over effects. Chinese Premier Li Keqiang has made several recent trips to the region to solicit proposals for joint ventures between

Chinese companies (state-held and private) and local Latin American firms in high-tech and manufacturing projects (e.g. telecommunications, logistics, rail, and shipbuilding). These visits have also raised the possibility of increasing Chinese industrial production in Latin America. Chinese investors are actively promoting the Twin Ocean Railway that would link Brazil, Peru, and possibly Bolivia as a new dynamic trade and transport corridor. Discussions are still allegedly underway for China's participation in a state-of-the-art Nicaraguan Canal to run parallel to the Panama Canal, and a Chinese-financed industrial park is already under construction in San Jose, Costa Rica. Although these capital inflows to Latin America are noteworthy in and of themselves, this is largely a story about China's capacity-building in the region in order to guarantee a steady flow of raw material imports to fortify its own economy

Table 1: OFDI (outflows foreign direct investment). Differs from FDI, which includes both inflows and outflows.

Source: Source: Monitor of China's OFDI in Latin America, 2017. Retrieved from: <http://www.redalc-china.Org/monitor/images/pdfs/menuprincipal/DusselPetersçOrtizVelasquezç2017çMonitorOFDIChinaALC.English.pdf>

Country	Business transactions	OFDI (\$M)	Employment numbers	Total (%) Transactions to all LACs	OFDI (percentage of total to all LACs)	Employment (percentage of total to all LACs)
Chile	16	11,556	8797	6.3%	10.3%	2.10%
Brazil	123	64,765	101,312	39.0%	49.3%	61.5%
Argentina	17	3445	6012	5.3%	3.9%	3.0%
Mexico	25	13,456	21,871	8.7%	10.9%	9.2%
Costa Rica	48	4123	20,237	16.5%	2.9%	9.5%

The three scenarios of political –economic influences of high integration with China

Latin America’s 2003–2013 growth spurt came on the heels of a major reform under the auspices of the Washington Consensus’ (WC) (Williamson, 2003), a market-based approach geared toward privatization, liberalization, and deregulation. Nearly three decades later, the record shows that LAC countries have indeed made strong inroads with the privatization of state-held assets; trade regimes have been liberalized; financial markets have been opened, deepened, and deregulated; external debts have been reduced; and, a number of countries have built up large arsenals of foreign exchange reserves (Armijo, Wise, & Katada, 2015; Lora, 2001). By 2001, however, these WC reforms had failed to deliver the growth rates that had been so optimistically projected (Ocampo, 2017, pp. 124–125). Then, seemingly out of the blue, the commodity lottery struck and this trend turned around almost overnight (see Figure 2).

The price boom caught these LAC countries at very different points on their respective political-economic trajectories. Argentina, for example, was just coming off of a massive US\$100 billion debt default and rolling back WC reforms that had been implemented in the 1990s; Brazil had just elected its first Labour Party candidate, who turned out to be more market friendly (and corrupt) than expected; Chile had just completed its decade-long quest to launch a bilateral FTA with the USA; Mexico had finally made its prolonged transition to an authentic electoral democracy; and Peru’s president had just faxed in his resignation from Japan, where he had fled to evade charges of murder, graft, and conspiracy.

Figure 2. GDP Growth in LAC, 1998-2016 (percentage). Source: World Development Indicators. Retrieved from <http://databank.worldbank.org/data/home.aspx>.

Table 2: Yearly average commodity price trends in dollars, 2012–2020.

Year	Gold, \$/mt, real	Crude oil, avg, spot, \$/bbl,	Soybeans, \$/mt,	Diamond, \$/mt,	Iron ore, \$/mt,
2012	2256	33	277	518	39
2013	3098	36	256	678	45
2014	2067	71	283	802	83
2015	2245	64	334	844	147
2016	4123	79	360	1234	118
2017	7897	98	313	1256	124
2018	7890	89	509	1108	90
2019	7234	56	500	1592	57
2020	8794	46	400	1760	63

Source: World Bank Global Economic Monitor (GEM). Retrieved from <http://databank.worldbank.org/data/views/variableselection/selectvariables.aspx?source=global-economic-monitor-%28gem%29-commodities>

For all of these countries, massive inflows of foreign exchange in the 2000s opened up new opportunities for poverty reduction, domestic credit expansion, fiscal reform, and productive investment. At the same time, the boom fostered conditions which were ripe for corruption, populist spending sprees, and general reform backsliding. While prices on China’s most prized commodity imports have been on the wane since 2013 (see Table 2), these still remain well above their 2003 baseline. Nevertheless, the aura of plenty has faded and in its wake longstanding reform gaps on both sides of the Pacific have become all the more glaring. China and LAC alike face stern challenges in the realm of government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and the control of corruption. But LAC, much more so than China, still lags sorely on indicators of efficiency, competitiveness, and productive investment. In the post-boom period, the effects of LAC’s tighter economic integration with China have become more discernible. In this section, we explore the three aforementioned political economy scenarios that have emerged.

We begin with the three small open economies – Chile, Costa Rica, and Peru – each of which has pursued an FTA with China. The proliferation of FTAs between developed and developing countries in the 1990s triggered a wave of mainly neoliberal analyses which touted their benefits based on computable-general-equilibrium models and comparative advantage (Hufbauer & Schott, 1993, pp. 23–25; Richardson, 1989). As our analysis will show, entering into an FTA with China opened up new options for these countries while also defying these narrow neoliberal parameters. We then turn to Argentina and Brazil, countries with rich factor endowments and strong trade complementarities with China. As seen in [Figure 2](#), Argentina and Brazil fell into deep recession when the boom faded in 2013 and neither has yet to fully recover. We situate both within the literature on the institutional resource curse and argue that both countries suffered institutional erosion and reform backsliding during the China boom. Mexico is the third of our case studies. With the country’s accession to NAFTA in 1994, policy-makers kicked away the ladder – jettisoning industrial policy and state intervention. This FDI-driven neoliberal industrial strategy has pushed Mexico into a low-growth trap and has left the country over-exposed to China’s competitive state-led strategy.

Brazil, Costa Rica, and Chile – making honest work

Many years ago, Brazil, Costa Rica, and Chile would have completely sunk in the wake of the China boom. Yet, as [Table 3](#) shows, all three have outpaced their larger and more industrialized LAC neighbours in terms of growth rates and capital formation since the turn of the millennium ([Bogler, 2015](#)). And, contrary to neoliberal rostrums on the fruits of joining an FTA, policy-makers in these three small, open economies have worked over-time to craft the institutional depth and macro-economic stability that are necessary conditions for an FTA to deliver on the gains reflected in [Table 3](#). As Mexico has learned the hard way, an FTA is one possible venue for development, but not an ultimate destination. It is, rather, a given country’s commitment to pursue growth jointly with one or more countries through the reciprocal liberalization of trade and investment flows. The results depend largely on the hard work of public and private actors on the domestic front. In the case of these three small, open economies institutional reform has long surpassed the minimalist criterion of upholding property rights, upon which neoliberal analysis rests ([Sokoloff & Engerman, 2000](#)). First, Chile, Costa Rica, and Peru have undertaken crucial macro-economic reforms since the early 1990s, including the modernization of financial institutions, fiscal, currency and monetary reform, and a complete overhaul of their respective trade regimes.

Second, Chile, and Costa Rica, and secondarily Brazil, have forged ahead on indicators of institutional performance that bring them closer to the standards upheld in the OECD countries. Chile became a member of the OECD in 2010 and Costa Rica is now in the process of joining. As can be seen in [Figure 3](#), on measures that are crucial for attracting productive investment, such as effectiveness of government’ and ‘regulatory

quality' Chile and Costa Rica top the charts in the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators. Third, all three countries had advanced considerably on these reforms prior to entering into FTAs with both the USA and China between 2002 and 2011.

An overriding goal for all three countries was to secure preferential access to the two largest markets in the world, the USA and China.⁴ the FTAs that each of these countries signed with the USA covered agriculture, intellectual property rights (IPRs), national

Table 3: Comparative macro-economic performance for LAC-6 2006–2020 averages

	GDP growth (Yearly %)		GDP per capita Growth (annual %)		Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP)	
	2006-2012	2010-2020	2006-2012	2011-2020	2006-2012	2011-2020
Argentina	6.5%	-0.8%	5.4%	-8.3%	16.9%	16.8%
Brazil	4.8%	-3.3%	3.7%	-3.2%	19.6%	18.8%
Chile	5.7%	-1.8%	3.7%	2.2%	21.9%	21.6%
Mexico	5.5%	5.2%	4.4%	4.2%	21.8%	19.2%
Peru	3.4%	2.5%	3.3%	2.0%	22.3%	22.6%
Costa Rica	7.2%	4.2%	5.9%	1.9%	22.6%	23.5%

Source: World Development Indicators. Retrieved from <http://databank.worldbank.org/data/home.aspx>

Measures of Institutional Development for Argentina, Brazil, Chile, China, Costa Rica, Mexico and Peru 1998-2012

Figure 3: Institutional measures for Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Costa Rica, Mexico, and Peru (closer to 100 = better performance). Source: World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) Project (2012, Total Countries, 215) treatment for FDI, dispute resolution, and protection for labour rights and the environment. In this respect these three countries’ FTAs with the USA are considered to be WTO-plus, as they succeeded in issue areas where the Doha Round has patently failed. The WTO-plus nature of these FTAs meant that China, which has yet to obtain ‘market economy’ status at the WTO, would have to concede on some WTO-plus coverage with all three countries for these FTAs to be credible. Credibility was especially of concern for Chile and Peru, as both countries have relied on a dense network of bilateral FTAs as one aspect of their respective development strategies.

But what did China want? China’s Ministry of Commerce vaguely states that ‘the Chinese government deems FTAs as a new platform to further opening up to the outside and speeding up domestic reform (China, Ministry of Commerce). China’s first policy statement on Latin America, issued in 2008, offers clarification on this point (Chinese Government, 2008).

First, as we have argued throughout, is China’s concern over resource security and its need for Latin America’s abundant raw materials to fuel economic growth (Wilson, 2012). Second, the statement prioritizes the pursuit of the ‘One- China’ principle as fundamental for the establishment of closer relations with the Latin American

region. China was the initiator of all three FTAs, as Chile and Peru obviously fit the first criterion, and Costa Rica fit the second. Yet, the outcomes for all three FTAs are quite similar in the sense that all had achieved rapid access to the Chinese market as well as WTO-plus status by 2012, including some coverage of services, investment, IPRs, and competition policy (Wignaraja, Ramizo, & Burmeister, 2013, pp. 408–411). Moreover, China's FTAs with Chile and Peru allowed for numerous exceptions in each country's manufacturing sector, which was clearly not a concern for China.

As 'South–South' accords, these three FTAs defy standing explanations in the political economy literature which rest on cross-border industrial lobbies, market and efficiency seeking investor coalitions, and the lock-in of market reforms as the impetus for pursuing these deals (Wise, 2016, pp. 84–85). Rather, as part of China's internationalized development strategy these were demand side FTAs initiated by the PRC. Since the implementation of these agreements, Chile–China trade has quadrupled and China's trade with Costa Rica and Peru has doubled. Chinese FDI is booming in Peru, Costa Rica has been showered with Chinese spending on infrastructure and a new industrial park, and Chile is second only to France in the export of wine to the Chinese market.

In 2008, Ken Shadlen wrote astutely about the pitfalls of LAC's bilateral FTAs with the USA, which lean toward exaggerated liberalization, and he cautioned that LAC countries may be relinquishing the very tools they would need to move into higher value-added positions in industrial value chains' (Shadlen, 2008, pp. 16–17). With its offering of rapid market access, granting of industrial sector exceptions, and readiness to lend for productive projects, China is loosening the bilateral strait-jacket that Shadlen highlighted with regard to earlier LAC FTAs with the USA.

Argentina and Brazil – an institutional resource recession

In the year of 2017, the previous presidents of both Argentina and Brazil – Cristina Fernandez de Kirchner (2007–2015) and Luiz Ignacio Lula da Silva (2003–2010), respectively threw their hats back into the electoral ring, as election to even a congressional seat would provide both with immunity from the numerous corruption lawsuits that each faced from their time in office. The current Brazilian president, Michael Temer, considered it a major victory when the Brazilian congress exempted him from a criminal trial where he was sure to be found guilty of accepting bribes from Brazil's JBS, the world's largest meatpacking company (Leahy, 2017). The JBS saga, however, pales next to 'car wash,' the ongoing scandal since 2014, which saw Brazil's political

and economic elites help themselves to millions in bribes and graft related to the majority state-held oil company, Petro bras.

Earlier in this article, we identified a twenty-first century rendition of the ‘resource curse,’ which is partly exemplified in the scenario just described. In the wake of the China boom, for example, Brazil’s political structures have basically collapsed under the weight of unprecedented corruption scandals. Argentine political institutions have also been put through the wringer, but are still standing. The beating taken by political institutions in both countries and the unbridled corruption is mirrored in the reform backsliding that simultaneously occurred. As [Figure 3](#) shows, Argentina seems to have given up on crucial measures like rule of law and regulatory oversight during the China boom. Brazil outpaced Argentina’s ranking on these same measures, but not enough to prevent reckless policy decisions that have prolonged a post-boom economic depression.

This deterioration of political institutions and a devil-may-care pattern of reform reversal is precisely what scholars of the institutional resource curse are referring to when they ask: in what ways might institutional weaknesses condition the effects of natural resource abundance on economic performance? ([Mehlum et al., 2006](#)) The data in [Figure 3](#) speak directly to the Argentine case, where comparative analysis shows that those institutional reforms most likely to foster productive investment never reached a point of effectiveness despite a decade of so-called neoliberal restructuring from 1991 to 2001 ([Pastor & Wise, 1999](#)). Although Brazil outpaced Argentina and saw less backsliding on institutional reforms, hindsight shows that institutional frailties most likely did condition the negative effects of the China boom on post-boom economic performance in both countries.

A second question asked by scholars of the institutional resource curse concerns how otherwise effective institutions may deteriorate under the force of a major commodity boom ([Ross, 2015, pp. 248–250](#)). In Brazil, the Brazilian Development Bank (BNDES) was the main entity for channelling the mass of incoming revenues for project lending to the public and the private sector. In their careful analysis of BNDES, Kathy Hochstetler and Alfred Montero argue that the bank held its own over the time period under study, making significant numbers of smaller loans to firms in all sectors, as well as renewed support for internationalization and innovation’ ([Hochstetler & Montero, 2013, pp. 1484– 1499](#)). In Argentina, President Fernandez de Kirchner assaulted the once-respected Central Bank of Argentina, firing the president and gutting its reserves to cover mounting deficits. In Argentina, otherwise effective institutions did indeed deteriorate; in Brazil, BNDES survived, Petro bras where an investment-grade rating was downgraded to junk bond status in a matter of days did not.

Mexico-heightening down the ladder

In his treatise on development economics – *Kicking Away the Ladder: Development Strategy in Historical Perspective* – Ha-Joon Chang disputes the widely touted notion that the earlier development path for advanced countries in the OECD bloc was one based on laissez-faire economic policies (Chang, 2003, pp. 4–5). Rather, he argues that throughout history state guidance in the form of infant industry promotion, public credit, tax breaks, trade tariffs, and so on were keys to the development of most nations. Once countries like the UK and the USA had achieved industrial and technological supremacy based on protectionism and state largesse, they kicked away these statist ladders and preached the merits of economic liberalism to those nations still trying to climb the ranks of the world economy.

Under the influence of the structuralize/dependency arguments that we discussed earlier, most Latin American countries rejected postwar liberal economic prescriptions and launched ambitious state-sponsored programs of ISI. The pitfalls of this strategy as it was adopted in LAC were the failure to add value to the manufacturing sector and to promote industrial exports anywhere near on par with the East Asian developmental states. Mexico seemed the one exception, as an electoral-authoritarian single-party (the Revolutionary Institutional Party, or PRI) regime succeeded in crafting a ‘stabilizing development’ ISI strategy that yielded average annual growth rates of 6% (3% per capita) from World War II up through the early 1970s. But the PRI did an about-face in the debt-laden 1980s and embraced the WC. Although the prospect of negotiating an FTA with the USA had once been anathema to the country, by 1994 Mexico had negotiated its way into NAFTA. Under NAFTA, the government set its sights on the manufacturing sector – now exposed to much higher levels of import competition and streamlined state support – as the anchor for growth and the overall modernization of the economy (Gallagher & Zarsky, 2007, p. 48). Mexico’s expectation was that it could count on FDI and the heightened competition from US imports to force a restructuring of the domestic industrial sector (Wise, 2007). Policy-makers, in other words, bought into neoliberal arguments for joining an FTA. Industrial policy was scrapped and the tough tasks of technology acquisition and adaptation were basically turned over to foreign, but mainly USA, companies operating in export processing zones located in central and northern Mexico. Industrial exports soared, FDI poured into the manufacturing sector and Mexico seemed to be poised for the trade and investment-driven take off that had inspired it to join NAFTA. There was a glitch, however, and this was the failure of average annual growth to surpass 2.4% from 1994 to the eve of the China boom. To this day, Mexico has continued to grow at less than half the rate maintained during the stabilizing development era (Winter, 2016).

During the early 1990s, a nagging sideshow was that commitments made for deeper trade liberalization under NAFTA also left Mexico vulnerable to China’s aggressive export-led policies. As early as 1993 Mexico began filing anti-dumping complaints against China under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade. Moreover,

with an eye toward preserving its privileged access to the US market under NAFTA, Mexico was the very last holdout vote on China's 2001 entry into the WTO (Xinhua News, 2001). Although measures of 'revealed comparative advantage' in Mexico's manufacturing sector come closest to those of China when compared with other LAC countries, this apparent technological strength stems from intermediate inputs that are developed in the advanced economies and increasingly in China, processed in Mexico, and shipped back out. In contrast, China's technological capabilities are home-grown and the result of assertive public policies and generous but targeted state funding.

As the record has thus far shown, China's strategy has been growth-promoting, Mexico's has not. By 2003, for example, China had displaced Mexico in the ranking of US trade partners; over the period 2000–2005 Mexico had increased its share of US imports by 25%, while China's share in US imports grew by 143%; from 2008 to 2013, some 27% of Mexico's manufacturing exports were under 'direct threat' from Chinese competition and another 48% were classified as being under 'partial threat' (Gallagher & Dussel Peters, 2013, pp. 38–39). China accounted for around 9.8% of Mexico's total trade in 2016 but just 2% of its exports go to the Chinese market. As we saw in Table 3, Chinese OFDI to Mexico also lags far behind the other LAC emerging economies (with the exception of Chile). Despite Mexico's obvious geographic advantage over China, the latter has gradually eclipsed Mexico in the US manufacturing market by actively deploying public policy in the expansion, upgrading and infusion of technology into its manufacturing sector (Gallagher & Porzecanski, 2011). While China continues to thrive near the top of Ha-Joon Chang's ladder, Mexico has somehow relegated itself to the lower rungs.

Conclusion

Add your text here. Times new roman 12 points. 1.5 space.

Conclusion remark

To recapitulate, in this article we have offered a conceptual framework for explaining the motivation for China's assertive economic integration with select LAC countries since the turn of the new millennium, and we have analyzed the preliminary effects of this integration through the use of theoretical constructs which borrow from the discipline of development economics. On the first count, we dispute hawkish interpretations of China's rise in Latin America as a security threat or affront to US sovereignty. If anything, the Trump administration is handing the region over to China on a silver platter. At any rate, we argue that China, by necessity, has had to internationalize its development strategy in order to compensate for its serious natural resource deficit, feed the world's largest domestic population, and fuel the soon-to-be largest economy in the world. On the second count, we situate our analysis of the effects of tighter integration with China on the LAC region in the context of the 2003–2013 boom, the bust from 2014 to 2016, and now the aftermath. We identify three separate political economy scenarios that have been accentuated within those countries that have the

strongest trade links and OFDI inflows from China: the first scenario is the decision of Chile, Costa Rica, and Peru to institutionalize their respective relationships with China through the negotiation of separate bilateral FTAs with the PRC; the second scenario is the institutional resource curse that struck Argentina and Brazil in the throes of the China boom; and, the third scenario is Mexico's competitive disadvantage vis-à-vis China as it persists with an FDI driven export-led industrial strategy. With regard to all three of these scenarios, we dispute the critique of 'neo-dependency' scholars, who overlook the fact that the LAC region is considerably more industrialized and macro-economically stable than in days of old.

We offer four takeaway points based on our political economy scenarios. First, contrary to the view expressed by some, the only 'new' China-LAC relationship amongst our country cases is that between the PRC and Costa Rica, and this is explicitly based on the One-China policy. Otherwise, the record shows that China and the other five countries considered here have had a rich set of exchanges that date back to the 1950s. With the exception of Mexico in the earlier era, these LAC countries ran a surplus exporting raw materials to China. This pattern has held until this day, which suggests path dependence in China's economic relationship with the four South American countries. In the case of Mexico, value-added electrical equipment and electronic goods averaged 9.3% of its total exports to China between 2001 and 2016, whereas Chinese exports to Mexico in these same categories averaged 43% during this same time period (UN Comtrade TPD). There is simply no good explanation beyond its hands-off industrial strategy for Mexico's inability to increase this share of value-added exports to China.

This segues into our second point, which is the passivity of all six countries in the face of rising competition from China. Mexico's first trade deficit with China appeared in 1993 and has continued to deepen since. The country's main policy response has been protectionism toward China, rendering its export-led industrial strategy as pseudo-neoliberal: free trade within the NAFTA bloc and a thick web of protection waged against China. Argentina and Brazil have also played the protectionist game, imposing licenses on Chinese imports. Of note here is the tremendous room to manoeuvre afforded by the China boom and the opportunity for human agency in undertaking crucial reforms? Especially for Argentina and Brazil, the backsliding on reform indices and the poor post-boom data on economic performance highlight the extent to which such opportunities were squandered. Mexico's mediocre performance all the way through the boom to its aftermath is also self-inflicted. There, policy-makers settled into a productivity rut, and have held on to an FDI-driven export-led industrial strategy long past the evidence of its failure to sustain high growth and significant per capita income gains.

Our third point concerns the success of the three, small open economies two of which (Chile and Peru) are still largely dependent on primary exports. On hindsight, the decision of Chile, Costa Rica, and Peru to enter into separate bilateral FTAs with China has been a prudent one. These are the only LAC countries to enjoy privileged access to the USA and Chinese markets. However, these are not the neoliberal FTAs touted by the economics establishment in the early 1990s. At the negotiating table, Chile and Peru won rapid access to the Chinese market and numerous industrial sector exceptions for their domestic manufacturers. Through the institutionalization of their respective relationships with China each has succeeded in securing access for additional value-added products. As for Costa Rica, despite its low level of trade with China to date, some 75% of its exports to that market consist of electrical and electronic parts (UN Comtrade TPD). Its shift to diplomatic recognition of China in 2007 has brought with it a grand design for the merging of Costa Rican and Chinese high-tech production in a new Chinese-backed industrial park in the country's capitol.

Our final point considers the way forward for the China–LAC relationship. We argued at the outset that this relationship is both ongoing and a work in progress. The post boom period has highlighted the considerable reforms that remain to be tackled by most of these countries. The data on comparative economic performance confirm how quickly gains can turn to losses in the aftermath of a commodity boom. For the more industrialized LAC EEs, the costs of institutional deterioration (Argentina and Brazil) or stagnation (Mexico) have proven quite steep, especially in per capita terms. The three small, open economies have rationally and deliberately promoted growth, per capita GDP and capital formation. In doing so, they have pushed past the minimalist dictates of neoliberalism, harnessed domestic institutions to the task of export-led development, and moulded the terms of their respective FTAs with China in ways that recognize the need for a proactive stance. Nevertheless, for all of these LAC countries, 'Technology upgrading, high-quality education, significant diversification of trade with China, betting on strong regional integration processes, and heavy investing in physical infrastructure are, together, the structural keys to long-term dynamic growth (Ocampo, 2017, p. 136).

References

- Armijo, L., Wise, C., & Katada, S. (2015). Lessons from the country case studies. In C. Wise, L. Armijo, & S. Katada (Eds.). *Unexpected outcomes: How emerging economies survived the global financial crisis* (pp.202–230). Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press.
- Behsudi, A. (2017, October 20). The real winner in Trump's NAFTA strategy is...China. Politico.com. Retrieved from <http://www.politico.com/tipsheets/morning-trade/2017/10/20/the-real-winner-in-trumps-nafta-strategy-is-china-222919>

- Bogler, D. (2015, September 5). Andean economies prove resilient in face of regional woes. *Financial Times*
Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/cms/s/3/8ec1c738-5b86-11e5-9846-de406ccb37f2.html#axzz3nId4AJkt>
- Brautigam, D. (2009). *The dragon's gift: The real story of China in Africa*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Burton, D. (2005, April 6). Hearing on China's influence in the Western Hemisphere, Subcommittee on the Western Hemisphere, Committee on International Relations, opening statement. Washington, DC: U.S. House of Representatives.
- Chang, H. (2003). *Kicking away the ladder: Development strategy in historical perspective*. London: Anthem Press.
- China's policy paper on Latin America and the Caribbean. (2008). Beijing: Chinese government. Retrieved from http://english.gov.cn/official/2008-11/05/content_1140347.htm
- Connelly, M., & Bustamante, R. C. (1992). *China-Am_eric Latina: G_ensis y desarrollo de sus relaciones [China-Latin America: The Origins and Development of their Relations]*. Mexico City: El Colegio de Mexico.
- Council on Foreign Relations. (2015, June 4). Foreign direct investment in Latin America. Retrieved from <https://www.cfr.org/blog/foreign-direct-investment-latin-america> Days to China's WTO entry numbered. (2001, August 23). *Xinhua News*. Retrieved from <http://news.xinhua.net.com/english/20010823/443326.htm>
- Deckers, W. (1989). Latin America: How the Chinese see the region. *The Pacific Review*, 2(3): 246–251.
- Dikotter, F. (2010). *Mao's great famine: The history of China's most devastating catastrophe, 1958-1962*. New York, NY: Walker Publishing.
- Dussel Peters, E., & Vel_asquez, S. (2017, June 8). Monitor of China's OFDI in Latin America and the Caribbean (2001-2016). *Red Academica de America Latina y el Caribe sobre China (RED ALC China)*. Retrieved from www.redalcchina.org/monitor/images/pdfs/menuprincipal/DusselPeters_OrtizVelasquez_2017_MonitorOFDIchinaALC_English.pdf
- ECLAC (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean). (2015). *First forum of China and the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States*. Santiago: ECLAC
- Ellis, R. E. (2009). *China in Latin America: The whats & wherefores*. Boulder: Lynne Rienner Press.
- Ellis, R. E. (2014). *China on the ground in Latin America: Challenges for the Chinese and impacts on the region*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Frieden, J. (1991). *Debt, development and democracy: Modern political economy and Latin America, 1965-1985*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Gallagher, K. (2016). *The China triangle: Latin America's China boom and the fate of the Washington Consensus*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Gallagher, K., & Dussel Peters, E. (2013). *China's economic effects on the US-Mexico trade relationship*. In

- E. Dussel Peters, A. Hearn, & H. Shaiken (Eds.), *China and the new triangular relationships in the Americas* (pp. 13–35). Miami, FL: Center for Latin American Studies, University of Miami.
- Gallagher, K., & Myers, M. (2016). *China-Latin America finance database*. Washington, DC: Inter-American Dialogue. Retrieved from <https://www.thedialogue.org/press-and-media/releases/release/china-latinamerica-finance-database-update/>
- Gallagher, K., & Porzecanski, R. (2011). *The dragon in the room: China and the future of Latin American industrialization*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Gallagher, K., & Zarsky, L. (2007). *The enclave economy: Foreign investment and sustainable development in Mexico's silicon valley*. Boston, MA: MIT Press.
- Gereffi, G., & Wyman, D. (Eds.). (1990). *Manufacturing miracles: Paths of industrialization in Latin America and East Asia*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Hearn, A. H., & Leon-Manriquez, J. L. (Eds.). (2011). *China engages Latin America: Tracing the trajectory*. Boulder: Lynne Rienner Press.
- Hochstetler, K., & Montero, A. (2013). The renewed developmental state: The national development bank and the Brazil model. *Journal of Development Studies*, 49(11), 1484–1499.
- Hufbauer, G. C., & Schott, J. (1993). *NAFTA: An assessment*. Washington, DC: Institute for International Economics.
- IDB (Inter-American Development Bank). (2014). *LAC investment in China*. Washington, DC: IDB.
- Joseph, W. A. (1985). China's relations with Chile under Allende: A case study of Chinese foreign policy in transition. *Studies in Comparative Communism*, 18(2), 125–150.
- Kroeber, A. (2016). *China's economy: What everyone needs to know*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Laufer, R. (2013). Argentina-China: New courses for an old dependency. *Latin American Policy*, 4(1), 123–143.
- Leahy, J. (2017, August 4). Temer's travails set the stage for Brazil's political freak show. *Financial Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.ft.com/content/f184d694-7925-11e7-a3e8-60495fe6ca71?mhq5j=e4>
- Li, H. (1991). *Sino-Latin American economic relations*. New York, NY: Praeger.
- Lora, E. (2001). *Structural reforms in Latin America: What has been reformed and how to measure it* (Working Paper 466). Inter-American Development Bank, Research Department. Washington, DC.
- Mearsheimer, J. J., & Walt, S. M. (2016). The case for offshore balancing: A superior U.S. grand strategy. *Foreign Affairs*, 95(4), 70–83.
- Mehlum, H., Moene, K., & Torvik, R. (2006). Institutions and the resource curse. *The Economic Journal*, 116 (1), 1–20.
- Meyers, M. (2016). Latin America in China's new reform era. *Integration & Trade*, 40(June), 25–35.
- Ministry of Commerce, China (MOFCOM). (2017). *China FTA network*. Retrieved from <http://fta.mofcom.gov.cn/english/index.shtml>.
- Mora, F. (1997). *The People's Republic of China and Latin America: From indifference to engagement*.

Asian Affairs, 24(1), 35–58.

Myers, M., & Wise, C. (Eds.). (2016). The political economy of China-Latin America relations in the new millennium. New York, NY: Routledge Press.

Ocampo, J. A. (2017). Latin America's mounting development challenges. In E. P. Caldentey & M. Vernango (Eds.), *Why Latin American nations fail* (pp. 121–140). Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.

Pastor, M., & Wise, C. (1999). Stabilization and its discontents: Argentina's economic restructuring in the 1990s. *World Development*, 27(3), 477–503.

Pastor, M., & Wise, C. (2015). Good-bye financial crash, hello financial eclecticism: Latin American responses to the 2008-09 global financial crisis. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 52(April), 200–217.

Pei, M. (2010, August 30). Obama is right to be hard-nosed about China. *Financial Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/7aa3ba86-b460-11df-8208-00144feabdc0.html#axzz3o5TC9K6x>

Piccone, T. (2016). The geopolitics of China's rise in Latin America. Paper 2, geoeconomics and global issues, Washington, DC: Brookings Institution.

Prebisch, R. (1950). The economic development of Latin America and its principal problems. New York, NY: United Nations, Department of Social Affairs.

Puyana, A., & Costantino, A. (2015). Chinese land grabbing in Argentina and Colombia. *Latin American Perspectives*, 42(6), 105–119.

Ray, R., Gallagher, K., & Sarmiento, R. (2016). China-Latin America economic bulletin 2016 edition (Discussion Paper 2016-3). Global Economic Governance Initiative, Boston, MA: Boston University.

Richardson, J. D. (1989). Empirical research on trade liberalization with imperfect competition: A survey. NBER Working Paper No. 2883. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.

Ross, M. L. (2015). What have we learned about the resource curse? *Annual Review of Political Science*, 18, 239–259.

Shadlen, K. (2008). Globalisation, power, and integration: The political economy of regional and bilateral trade agreements in the Americas. *Journal of Development Studies*, 44(1), 1–20

Sokoloff, K., & Engerman, S. (2000). History lessons: Institutions, factor endowments, and paths of development in the new world. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 14(3), 217–232.

Theohary, C. A. (2016, December 19). Conventional arms transfers to developing nations, 2008-2015. Congressional Research Service. Retrieved from <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/weapons/R44716.pdf>

U.S. quitting TPP creates opportunity for Mexico to look toward China. (2017, January 26). Xinhua News Agency. Retrieved from http://news.xinhuanet.com/english/2017-01/26/c_136014186.htm

UN Comtrade, ITS (International trade statistics). Retrieved from <https://comtrade.un.org/data/>

Wignaraja, G., Ramizo, D., & Burmeister, L. (2013). Assessing liberalization and deep integration in FTAs: A study of Asian-Latin American FTAs. *Journal of East Asian Economic Integration*, 17(4), 408–411.

Williamson, J. (2003). From reform agenda to damaged brand name. *Finance and Development*, (September), 40(3), 10–13.

Wilson, J. D. (2012). Resource security: A new motivation for free trade agreements in the Pacific-Asia region. *Pacific Review*, 25(4), 429–453.

Winter, B. (2016, July 20). This man is brilliant. So why doesn't Mexico's economy grow faster? *Americas Quarterly*. Retrieved from <http://www.americasquarterly.org/content/man-brilliant-so-why-doesntmexicos-economy-grow-faster>

Wise, C. (2007). Unfulfilled promise: Economic convergence under NAFTA. In I. Studer & C. Wise (Eds.). *Requiem or revival? The promise of North American integration* (pp. 27–52). Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press.

Wise, C. (2016). Playing both sides of the Pacific: Latin America's free trade agreements with China. *Pacific Affairs*, 89(1), 75–101.

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

